

THE IMPORTANCE OF VARIOUS FACTORS TO ACQUIRE A SECOND LANGUAGE

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Annotation: The article provides information about several distinct factors that play paramount of importance in the acquisition of a second language. The influence of each factor will be clarified separately which will give precise data to readers. The provided article will be effective for language instructors since teaching foreign languages requires a lot of efforts and patience from a teacher. Therefore, being informed with the article, language instructors will learn to consider several important factors while teaching a new language.

Key words: positionality, indexicality, gender, sexuality, race, ethnicity, racial profiling, social status

Introduction

Danesi (2000) noted that «sociolinguistics is the branch of linguistics studying how language functions in society. Sociolinguists study how linguistic forms and uses vary according to age, class, gender, situation, and other social variables» (p.214). The statement provides a reader with a clear explanation of the term sociolinguistics and how language is used by the influence of different social factors. From this definition it is obvious that the following article will cover the data that is associated with language and its usage in various circumstances. To be more precise, the article will clarify some specific key factors that are essential for the usage of language and some pedagogical implications which will be quite efficient for the language improvement of the learners. The article specifically observes regional, social, sexual, gender, ethnic and racial factors which influence the acquisition of a second language. Each factor is described by taking into account the terms such as positionality and indexicality which are the central points of the writing. The statements are scientifically proven as well as

the writer's own views and explanations. The writer proves his views with some relevant examples to make the statements more comprehensible for a reader. The provided pedagogical implications which explains a particular topic in sociolinguistics makes the work more accessible both for language instructors and learners.

Learner profile

The learners whom I am targeted at teaching are secondary school students who are on the verge of graduating 8th grade. Five of the students are the male ones, the rest five of them are girls. Most of them are between the ages of 14 – 15 and majority of them from Kashkadarya specifically from Karshi. When it comes to their nationalities, three of them are Russian (Danil, Aleksey and Kristina) ,one of them is Azerbaijan (Karina), one of them is Kazakh (Daler) and the rest five of them are Uzbek. When it comes to divide them according to their social status, five of Uzbek students are from well-income families but the rest five are middle-class and it is obvious that all of them are single. Regarding their language background, nearly all of them are learning the language for more than a year apart from that all of them are bilingual who can speak Uzbek, Russian and some them German or Spanish. Five of the learners are from Uzbek ethnicity and the rest part are from Russian, Azerbaijan and Kazakh. Crystal (1999) noted that «sociolinguistics is a branch of linguistics which studies the ways in which language is integrated with human society (specifically, with reference to such notions as race, ethnicity, class, sex, and social institutions). The subject is often distinguished from sociology of language, which tends to operate from the viewpoint of sociology, and (especially in Europe) from sociological linguistics which aims to see language as an integral part of sociological theory» (p.311). By reading this statement, from sociolinguistic point, I have realized to consider race, ethnicity, gender and social status of my learners before teaching them with a particular method to learn their L2. Moreover, the statement is the proof of dividing my learners according to their ethnicity and social status.

Social factor (different regions)

Harold Orton and Nathalia Wright (1974) noted that «A primary aim of linguistic geography is to reveal the occurrence and distribution of speech usages, especially those characteristic of particular regions. Their diffusion can be mapped clearly and simply. Close study of the resultant maps permits significant deductions to be drawn about the movements of those usages: whether, for example they are spreading or contracting, or whether, indeed, they have been partly supplanted by other features» (p.21). According to their view, it seems that identifying the learners according to their geographical location also plays an essential role on the acquisition of their L2. As for their positionality, those who are from mainly Karshi are a bit impolite and quite direct. They have less potential to educational sphere because they are much better at running private business. In most cases they take everything for granted and might not appreciate the hard work of people. However, the ones who are from Chirakchi are really diligent and more polite. They are more adaptable to new locations and try to be sociable. They try to imitate to urban people in terms of acting in public places and clothing style. The ones whose language background is Russian despite living in Karshi have totally different attitudes. They are naturally a bit arrogant and quite strict towards themselves. They think over thoroughly before making serious decisions.

Concerning their indexicality, those who are from Karshi use the words and sentences in a short way. Their accent and style of speech are seemed rude to people. They often use sarcasm and dialect words in their daily communication. They often avoid speaking in a literal way. Those that are from Chirakchi have the same style of speech but there are some differences in their accent and adding suffixes. Unlike Karshi people, they pronounce English pronoun «I» in Uzbek language as «**min**» and pronoun «you» as «**sin**» while those who are from Karshi pronounce them as «**man**» and «**san**». In addition to this, the pronunciation of their ending suffixes is totally different. For instance, they pronounce English verbs «**come**» and «**go**» with the pronoun «**we**» in their own language as «**boryapmiz**», «**kelyapmiz**» whereas Karshi people pronounce the verbs as «**boromiz**», «**kelomiz**». This mentioned part clearly relates to the term

«Dialectology» which was defined by Crystal (1995) who thoroughly observed the term by supporting strong points.

When it comes to the influence of their L1 pronunciation to the L2 learning process, those who are from Karshi can face fewer problems in terms of pronunciation. They are quite good at imitating the pronunciation of Englishmen and their body language. Their way of learning can be easier thanks to some received words such paynet, phone (telefon), printer (printer), boutique (butik) and other words. However those who are from Chirakchi usually face some problems in acquiring L2 due to strong influence of their local pronunciation. This is not the only case, in my teaching observations I have realized that those who are from rural areas have less potential to acquire languages since they are much better at learning science, math and physics.

Social factor (social status)

As for their family status, all of the learners are single so they are very confident and definite in their ideas. However, those who are middle-class are tend to be very polite, less confident in their acts and behave in a modest way. Whereas, well-income students are a bit arrogant and think they are dominant over others. The position of being single and wealthy give them double confidence on themselves which makes them think that they have rights for everything and anything. They usually look really satisfied and pleased with everything that surrounds them.

The important part of indexicality of those who are single, they mostly joke and try to use less polite style of speech. Using jokes while talking still depends on their personalities rather than their family status. Apart from that middle-class learners are very careful about the usage of words in their communication. It means they try to be polite and kind towards others. When they want to ask about something they usually use «**please**» and «**would you mind.....?**». Whenever they want to refuse something they say «**I am afraid I can` t**». These are the clear speaking features of middle class students. However, well-income learners often use some rude style of speech. They may sound boastful and rarely use apologizing words even if they can do something

wrong. They are likely to use some vulgar words or make unbearable jokes that can make their friends disappointed. But still it depends on their personalities and behavior.

Regarding the influence of social status to the acquisition of L2 is that being single learners can allocate more than enough time to their learning process. They are totally free of serious family responsibilities and extra outer influences. However, they are more likely to be engaged having fun with their friends and wasting their time for unnecessary activities. Turning to the impact of economic status, middle class learners tend to show more enthusiasm towards acquiring and they put all their efforts in order to achieve their target. Whereas, well-income students have less interest towards learning process since they are more occupied with entertaining activities. They usually ignore studying hard and learning vocabulary therefore they often search the easiest ways of learning without any struggling.

Gender and sexuality

With regard to gender positionality of the learners female students are really active and impatient. They usually try to provide quick responses and be quite emotional in some circumstances. They may overemphasize some situations and try to be in the center of attention. Because of being less tolerant they may face some problems while communicating. However, male students are calm enough and try to provide their responses in a slower way. They seem less active and patient. They try to depend on their mind rather than their feelings when they have to make an important decision. They are naturally tend to be leaders as they are less dubious in their responses and decisions.

Rocheftort (1665) noted that «The men have a great many expressions peculiar to them, which the women understand but never pronounce themselves. On the other hand, the women have words and phrases which the men never use, or they would be laughed to scorn. Thus it happens that in their conversations it often seems as if the women had another language than the men». Therefore, by differentiating their indexicality according their gender, it seems that female students sound more polite with lower tones while speaking. They are more talkative and sometimes speak more

than enough. Because of being emotional, they avoid speaking monotonously by rising and lowering tones within speaking. They are bad at reading and writing since they are impatient to read the whole reading passages. They are less capable in writing complex sentences with strong supportive sentences because of possessing less knowledge about other subjects. However, male learners seem a bit impolite as their voice is rough. They speak less but provide clear-cut responses for questions. Their deep voice can attract the audience easily. Even though they seem less attentive, they thoroughly analyze the speech of their peers and mates. In spite of having some problems with fluency while speaking, they can express their ideas with strong arguments and good reasons. The same is true for their writing skills, they provide strong supportive ideas and are able to write grammatically complex sentences with good coherence and cohesion.

Concerning how their gender has an impact on their language learning process, female learners can acquire much faster thanks to their diligence and deep enthusiasm. They are quite eager to learn every single detail and do all the tasks that are given at home. They sometimes perform extra tasks besides the ones that are given by an instructor. They tend to have good oral skills rather than the other ones. They always learn the words by hard but because of having shortterm memory they have to revise them constantly. However, male learners naturally possess higher IQ which gives them opportunity to have good memory. It means that their vocabulary aspect is comparatively better. Because of having good critical thinking, they are much better at speaking in a grammatically accurate way. But because of being lazy they often put off their tasks which later may cause some serious issues.

Bucholtz and Hall (2004) noted that «sexuality is no more asocial than gender and that both are inseparable from matters of power». Regarding their sexual positionality female learners usually try to be seemed extremely polite and positive in the existence of their opposite genders. They try to avoid gossiping and using some words that have negative meaning. Sometimes they try to correct the mistakes of male students to show how careful and attentive they are. The same is true for male learners

that in the existence of girls they try to avoid using vulgar words and some slangs that are common only among male genders. They try to show themselves only from positive sides.

In terms of their indexicality female genders try to speak less by giving turns to their peers or mates. Moreover, in the existence of their opposite genders they try to make fewer mistakes while speaking or expressing their ideas. They are very careful in selecting proper words while expressing their views. They tend to show that they have good lexical resource and grammar by trying to make up complicated sentences with high level words. Whereas male genders are quite honest and fair that they usually dislike pretending to have good knowledge even in the absence of female learners. Precisely, they show that what they are actually capable to do. Furthermore, they do not overemphasize any of their language skills as well the aspects. But, still they try to focus on their pronunciation by imitating foreigners to show that how good they are in pronouncing even difficult words.

Considering the influence of sexuality in the process of acquiring the language it can be mentioned that female learners might have dominance in speaking since they tend to speak a lot, provide some opinions regardless of their validity. They tend to make more mistakes due to being hasty. Still, they can learn much faster by absorbing huge amount of information at once. However, they have less efficiency and quality in their learning. However, the learning process of male learners occurs a bit slowly compared to female since they try to learn more thoroughly by taking into account every detail. One clear example can be the approach of learning new words. Male learners try to learn fewer words but with examples and their usage in sentences. But female learners try to focus on the number of words that they have learned rather than how effectively they learned them.

Race and ethnicity

Edley (2001) noted that «Race is not rocket science. It's harder than rocket science». By mentioning Edley's words it is seen that race has also plays a significant role in acquiring a language. Justice Cooper observed that « "racial profiling" is based

on visual cues that result in the confirmation or speculation of the racial background of an individual, or individuals». Seven of the learners are Asian and their racial profiling helps to identify that they are white with dark black hair. They have thick eyebrow and smiling face that can make anyone happy. They are not very tall clearly they have modest appearance. By their racial profiling one can think that they are not Asian but somehow European.

With regard to indexicality, there is not a big difference in their language profiling as they possess quite a similar style of speech. They are extremely polite and most of them have monotonous style that can be boring for a listener. Even though they seem polite, they rarely use words «**please**», «**would you mind**» and others. As a symbol of respect toward the names of people they add suffix «**jon**» to the ending part of males` names. For example, Ilhomjon, A`zamjon, Bekhruzjon. For females` names they add «**hon**». For instance, Feruzahon, Munisahon and etc.

The same is true for the influence of learning process, nearly all of them are adaptable to acquire new languages. They can easily receive foreign accent and pronunciation since Asian people are good at imitating in any foreign languages. Furthermore, they face fewer problems in learning grammar since the basics of most languages is similar to Asian language.

According to some research ethnicity cannot be studied or understood outside the context of other social variables, such as social class or gender. Relying on this idea, it seems that ethnicity cannot be separated from other social factors while considering language acquisition. For this reason, regarding the ethnicity of the learners, the ones whose background is Russian are totally different from Uzbek learners. Even though they have lived in Karshi for a long time, they have completely different attitudes. For instance, they are quite honest and fair. They cannot tolerate when they face unfair approach. They are less polite and careful towards people surrounding them. They tend to lead lonely lifestyle being away from their family. However, they do each of their work in a thorough way not missing any minor detail. However, the ones who are from Uzbek ethnicity are less responsible towards their

work. And they have to skip unfair situations despite facing them with their own eyes. They have the phobia of telling the real truth or saying as it happens or exists. But, they are very hospitable, friendly and they are not careless towards surrounding people regardless of their age and relationship to them. Moreover, they always respect the elderly and show their great admiration to them.

As for indexicality, the learners of Russian background usually speak fast and shorten their words. They have to soften the words when there is a sign of softening. They usually do not follow strict grammar rules while speaking. Their style of speech does not seem very polite or quite rude and their tone of speech is a low. Uzbek learners also shorten their words and sentences but it depends on people whom they are talking. They do completely follow exact grammar rules of their own language while communicating. It is very pity that most of them are not aware of the grammar of their own native language because of studying in a Russian class.

Regarding the influence of their ethnicity to language learning process, it can be mentioned Russian learners can face more difficulties with pronunciation because of addicting to use a sign of softening in their words. Besides that they may face some problems to addict to learn all the four skills as Russian language is associated with teaching mostly grammar and literature. Unlike them, Uzbek learners can easily receive foreign pronunciation and adapt it structure. They are not strictly addicted to their native language which means they can smoothly move from one language to another. However, because of not having perfect grammar knowledge in their own language, they might face some problems to acquire the grammar in a required way.

Learning context

With regard to their learning context, they study at secondary school number 9 which is located at the central part of Karshi city. The school is not specialized in teaching foreign languages but considered as one of the most prestigious schools.

The students took their background knowledge during primary school years when they were provided with basic and fundamental part of the language. However, the essential part of the language they acquired at private study centers where they were

taught in a thorough way. The learners mostly taught in a deductive way since the teachers of local schools are not experienced in teaching inductively.

Prabhu (1990) noted that « there is no best method and what really matters is the need for teachers to learn to operate with some personal conceptualization of how their teaching leads to desired learning-with a notion of causation that has a measure of credibility for them» (p.172). Actually, according to Prabhu there are not any best methods and the most important thing is conducting a lesson properly considering the level and the needs of target learners. However, still they had to be instructed with some particular ways so they were mostly taught with grammar translation and audio-lingual methods. Through grammar-translation method they are able to improve their grammatical competence and vocabulary skills. Audio-lingual method will help them to improve their listening as well as their speaking skills. They were accepted individual approaches when they faced some problems with the acquisition of difficult topics. Moreover, they were instructed to learn the language with collaborative approach which means they worked in groups or in peers and gave comments to each other. The teacher tried to emphasis on teaching all four skills with the help of a particular book and additional handouts. Still, the instructor paid more attention on grammatical and vocabulary aspect of the language rather than focusing the other four skills. Since Stephen Krashen concluded that «The effects of grammar teaching..... are peripheral and fragile». In addition to this Richards, Renandya (2002) noted that «People now agree that grammar is too important to be ignored, and that without a good knowledge of grammar, learners` language development will be severely constrained» (p.145). According to the statements of both authors, it seems that regardless of being boring way of teaching, grammar is the basis of a language which provides fundamental knowledge.

Turning to their motivation, Edward Deci (1975) noted that « intrinsically motivated activities are ones for which there is no apparent reward except the activity itself. Intrinsically motivated behaviors are aimed at bringing about certain internally rewarding consequences, namely, feelings of competence and self-determination»

(p.23). From the statement of Edward Deci, it seems the learners are intrinsically motivated which means that they have full potential to motivate themselves and can rarely be impacted by external factor. Furthermore, taking the international certificate of IELTS is also the target that is set on their own which proves that how determined they are. Most of them have the purpose of taking this certificate since they want to study at the most prestigious universities. Furthermore, the certificate can give the opportunities to participate in various global programs and have a prosperous future with high-income jobs. All in all, the mentioned reasons are mainly considered as extrinsic motivation which has triggered the learners to put all their efforts to the acquisition of the language in a perfect way.

When it comes to their investment, Norton (1995) noted that «investment is primarily sociological and focuses on how histories, lived experiences and social practices shape language learning» (p.17). The statement identifies that investment observes the process of learning a language. Moreover, David and Norton (2005) emphasized the question «Are students invested in the language practices of the classroom or community? » (p.37). The question makes even more precise that the students have done their best to learn the language efficiently. They were very responsible towards the lessons that they tried not to miss any lessons except force major situations. They had to devote their whole time when they were occupied with huge amount of homework. Besides that they had to manage their time appropriately in order to catch up with other responsibilities that they possessed. Organizing speaking clubs with their peers or classmates and allocating much money for the materials that they had to learn were also their great efforts towards the acquisition of the language. After the lesson, they had a voice chat in several English channels and had a chat with foreigners via social networking sites.

Within the period of their learning process they have been able to improve their pronunciation and speaking. They have learned how to express their ideas in a grammatically correct way and also they have broadened their horizon about various topics and fields. They are quite good at imitating foreigners which helped to receive

their pronunciation much more easily. Considering these facts, speaking, pronunciation and critical thinking are the main advantages of the learners. In spite of performing lots of listening tasks, they still have some problems in doing some exercises even «filling in gaps». They have been provided with the clear ways of listening successfully and how to make a right approach while doing it but still they need to improve their comprehension. Moreover, because of not being aware of enough vocabulary, they have a problem with the comprehension of reading passages and responding the questions of those passages in a proper way. For these reasons, their receptive skills can be their weak points.

Sociolinguistic profile of the Context where English will be used

With regard to the usage of language according to their positionality, the learners are supposed to use the acquired language at one of the most prestigious universities of a particular foreign country. Nearly all of the learners are planning to move Britain to study at Oxford university. Those who are from Russian ethnicity are quite direct, honest and very responsible towards any work regardless of its necessity which is the prior demand of the university they have selected. Their behavior, attitudes and outlook about life partly correspond to the British so they can easily get on well when they pay a visit. For instance, Russians` style of living is nearly similar to Europeans. Precisely, they prefer to lead lonely lifestyle and in most families teenagers will be totally independent after the age of 18. It means that they will not be dependent on their parents even when they make up serious decisions. However, those whose background is Uzbek, have totally different mentality, outlook and behavior. To be more exact, in Asian culture, specifically in Uzbekistan, despite being independent, teenagers or adults still follow the advice of the elderly and rely on their lifelong experience. The value of family traditions is the priority of Uzbek people and they have not adapted to have lonely lifestyle. Taking these facts into account, Russian students can easily adapt to foreign atmosphere and lifestyle which means they can use their L2 in a more confident way. Whereas Uzbek learners can undergo some difficulties until they get

accustomed to foreign culture and lifestyle which a bit negatively affect to the performance of their L2.

When it comes to the influence of their L1 to the usage of their L2, Russian learners may face more difficulties in terms of accurate pronunciation in their L2. Precisely, there is a sign of softening in Russian alphabet which is mostly added to the ending part of verbs. It means that due to the influence of their L1, they tend to soften most sounds and words in their L2 speech. This can cause difficulties in pronouncing English words accurately when they are abroad.

Moreover, it may cause some serious problems while using their L2 at university in an academic way. For instance, while making presentations or providing formal speech, they are supposed to use the language appropriately with accurate pronunciation. However, because of the impact of their L1 pronunciation, they can cause some inconveniences for the listeners and their professors to comprehend their speech in a proper way. When it comes to the usage of language in public places, they will face fewer challenges since they have learned all the necessary phrases, expressions that are useful for their communication. Regarding to Uzbek learners, although they may struggle with adapting entirely new atmosphere and lifestyle, they are good at expressing their ideas with correct version of pronunciation and grammar. It means that Uzbek learners have more competence in performing language appropriately. Moreover, their speech will be more understandable for locals since Uzbek tend to imitate foreigners more easily.

Pedagogical implications

By considering all the above mentioned facts and data, I would teach my learners the major phonological variables of consonant [r]. I would teach them mainly with audio-lingual method as by hearing constantly their ears can adapt to the correct version of pronouncing [r]. I will try to conduct through an inductive approach as to make the lesson more entertaining and make the learners think by themselves. For instance, I will show them at least 5 videos and ask them take notes they points. Following this, I will ask them about the main idea of all videos or what they are

emphasizing on. By considering their opinions, I will provide the exact response. Inductive method is also a good way of improving students` critical thinking. The most appropriate technique to teach the topic will be role playing because by playing the role of American and British people, students can clearly differentiate the usage of [r] in their communication and they will clearly understand which nation mostly use [r]. I would rather cover mostly listening and speaking skills. Because from the topic it is obvious that students can use [r] without hesitation when they listen it exactly from native speakers and they can use it appropriately in their speech and words when they practice it a lot in their speaking. Regarding the aspect of language, I would mostly emphasize on pronunciation and vocabulary as the sound variable can be clearly defined when it is pronounced in a right way in different words. The most proper tech for the acquisition of [r] will be COCA and Kahoot since learners can practice the correct pronunciation via entertaining techs. With the help of Kahoot the instructor can create more entertaining exercises that can be more understandable for the learners. As for the assessment part, they will be assessed in a holistic way by ranking. For example, each learner will be given five words and asked to differentiate phonological variable of [r]. For each correct answer they will be given two points. The maximum score will be 10 and the winner will not get any home task.

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